

FAIR Data Management Plan

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About this data management plan

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12-06-2024	Initial version
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Sensitive/personal data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> I will work with personal data (anonymized)
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1. Data capture

1.1 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The research has 3 objectives:

- To understand the presence of citizen science online.
- To understand citizen science from different perspectives.
- To understand the process of designing activities and how the data extracted supports the inspiration of this process.

The collection of data collected or generated as part of the research for each pathway following the FAIR principles has been as follows:

Objective 1 [OB1]: Data extracted from websites or online platforms about citizen science projects (e.g. eu-citizen.science) by means of a crawler or robot following the access and extraction restrictions set by each platform. They have been classified following specific metadata standards (e.g. PPSR_Core metadata standard) and data protection law (GDPR) and stored in a non-relational database (MongoDB) within Pompeu Fabra's servers. The data collected will be categorized using data mining methods such as Name-Entity recognition. Centralising the data in a single repository will facilitate future data analysis and enable other stakeholders, such as educators, to explore the data in ways that were previously not possible.

Dataset description OB1: CS projects data classified in categories (multiple languages (such as EN or ES)) and software developed for data extraction and classification.

Objective 2 [OB2]: The analysis of the data extracted from online platforms (Objective 1), posts published in X social media and questionnaires anonymized will be used to understand the connections between CS and education. And understanding the potential usages this information obtained and data extracted might have into formal education contexts. Collaborators from the research project would be the ones in charge of collecting the data and analysing it.

Dataset description OBJ2: CS projects dataset mentioned in objective 1, responses from the questionnaire and posts extracted from X social media network.

Objective 3 [OB3]: Anonymised data has been collected in workshops with secondary school teachers and Technology Enhance Learning (TEL) experts. Teachers and TEL experts will be the ones who generate the datasets. Those might be in Catalan, Spanish or English

Dataset description OBJ3: responses from the questionnaires, learning activity designs, illustrations, card sorting results, video recording of their screen without personal images, audio recordings of the interviews and an exploratory tool that will contain open data (detailed in 1.2).

1.2 Will you re-use any existing data, and what will you re-use it for?

For **OBJ1**, the software developed by academic contributors for data classification and data mining will be reused.

For **OBJ2**, existing data from questionnaires collected by academic contributors (from JYU university, Peltoniemi et al., 2023) and data extracted from X social media accounts that mention CS projects or published by CS projects accounts by academic contributors (from Rey Juan Carlos university) of the CS Track project will be used in specific.

The exploratory tool (**OBJ3**) will contain images from open images repositories and data about real problems related to SDGs from ourworldindata.org content from the educational platforms abpxods.cat and ildeplus.upd.edu will be integrated in the tool to improve design and user experience.

1.3 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The majority of the data will be in ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) data files, comma separated variable (CSV) format, which can be imported into rich-text files for word-processing or into spreadsheets. Data will be generated in the following formats:

- Pictures: jpeg, png
- Tables: xlsx
- Text: docx, pdf, txt
- Video: mp4, mkv
- Audio: mp4, aac
- SQL database: *.frm , *.myd and *.myi
- No-SQL database: BSON
- Exploratory tool: php, json, js, css, html
- Software: .py, .ipynb

1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use

< 10 GB

10-30 GB

30-50 GB

50 GB-250 GB

250 GB-500 GB

500 GB-2 TB

2 TB

2. Data processing and security

2.1 Indicate the restrictions (commercial, ethical or confidentiality) that may affect your data.

CS projects data classified dataset from OBJ1: On the one hand, data extraction was done following the robot exclusion protocol (Kolay et al., 2008), complying with the requirements of each website for data access and extraction. On the other hand, in order to comply with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the data were anonymised so as not to store personal data. We considered a dataset to be anonymised following the criteria of Gruschka et al., (2018).

All the datasets provided by collaborators for OBJ2: For those data questionnaires, they followed the guidelines of the Finnish National Research Integrity Board. The university JYU, to which they belonged, had a Human Sciences Ethics Committee that supported them. All data that transferred shall be either pseudoanonymised or completely anonymised. The Data Owner/Data Provider is responsible for the anonymization or pseudoanonymisation process and for ensuring that identifiable variables are not transferred.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: the protocols followed by the TIDE-UPF group (Hernández-Leo et al., 2023), following the UPF CIREP guidelines. All the data will be collected and traced that every participant have signed the agreement for data collection. After validation, the data will be stored pseudoanonymized for the analysis. Nevertheless, a copy of those datasets will be completely anonymised and published in open Zenodo private, under access request.

2.2 Main data security risks

CS projects data classified dataset and software developed from OBJ1: Data extracted will be stored in the Virtual Machines static data in Poblenou Campus (UPF IT servers) and to the Google Drive associated to the UPF and CS Track project accounts. The risk associated to the access and reading of data or data theft.

All the datasets provided by collaborators for OBJ2: the X posts will be stored into the Google Drive associated CS Track project accounts. The risk associated to the access and reading of data or data theft. Although data is shared by collaborators anonymise, there could be risk of reidentify persons.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: From the personal data collected through the questionnaires, learning designs, video recordings or audio recordings, although data is anonymised, there could be risk of reidentify persons. Additionally, there is a risk of losing the last version of the exploratory tool and the data contained in it in case failure of the server where it is hosted. Furthermore, as not being allow to select the server location in Hostinger, there is a risk that the place where it is stored does not follow the European law of GDPR and others data protection rules.

2.3 Where will you store the data?

The data is stored in the UPF IT Servers or CS Track Google Drive: Word documents related to the studies developed during the PhD research, excels with the data collected and analysed, images, videos or audio and other files. Software developed will be stored in GitHub repository.

In a MongoDB database in a Docker container in a Virtual Machines static data in Poblenu Campus: we stored all the data extracted from online platforms classified based on PPSR_Core metadata standard categories.

In Hostinger (<https://www.hostinger.es/>), a web hosting services: it contains the webpage developed with wordpress. This webpage contains all the information related to CS projects, real problems and activities developed by other teachers collected from online repositories. Hostinger servers are located in France, Lithuania, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, India, Indonesia, Singapore, USA or Brazil¹.

2.4 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

It is essential to control access and manage folder permissions for sensitive information in Google Drive. To avoid loss of data, all those involved in the project have to work on a shared account or unit and not on an individual basis.

From the data stored in the Virtual Machines static data in Poblenu Campus:

- Local backup on Campus Poblenu: from Mon to Sat, at 09:00PM retained 6 days. On Sundays, at 09:00PM and retained 3 weeks
- Remote transfer to Jaume Primer Datacenter: Everyday at 10:00PM and retained 2 weeks
- Backups are processed automatically based on NetApp snapshot technology (SnapVault) service on a time-scheduled basis.
- Standard recovery processes are available: CIFS sharing (previous versions), NFS exports, Qtree and volume restore.

The data exploration tool will be monthly backed up. The last backup will be stored in the Hostinger server and uploaded to the GitHub repository.

GitHub will be the repository to store the software code after every update during the code development.

2.5 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

¹ <https://support.hostinger.com/en/articles/1583267-where-are-hostinger-servers-located> (Access June 26th 2024)

All the material and data generated, at the end of the research, will be shared in Zenodo, but the sensitive material will be published anonymised and on demand.

3. Making data findable, including provisions of metadata

3.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

CS projects data classified dataset from OBJ1: Data extracted will be stored in Zenodo with a DOI identifier.

All the datasets provided by collaborators for OBJ2: data won't be published due to contain sensible data.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: anonymised data of questionnaires, learning activity designs, illustrations and card sorting results will be published in Zenodo with a DOI identifier.

3.3 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The data in the MongoDB database will be classified following the [PPSR Core metadata standard](#).

All the data published in Zenodo follows the Dublin core schema by European repository OpenAIRE.

All the software code will be published in GitHub and will contain related documentation and metadata information.

4. Making data accessible

4.1 Do you have any restrictions for sharing data in relation to the current regulation (General Data Protection Regulation) or others (ethical, commercial, security, intellectual property or copyright)?

CS projects data classified dataset and software developed from OBJ1: All the data will be made available in Zenodo without restriction access. Nevertheless, to comply with the GDPR and ethical regulations it will be fully anonymised following the criteria of Gruschka at al., (2018). The software developed for data extraction and classification will be published open in GitHub.

All the datasets provided by collaborators for OBJ2: Although data was anonymised, due to ethical restrictions won't be published by academic collaborators.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: A copy of the datasets will be published in Zenodo anonymised under request. The exploratory tool will be published in GitHub.

4.2 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The basis of the **objective 1** is to extract and store the data about citizen science projects shared online in multiple websites, classified into categories based on the PPSR_Core metadata standard. This data will be reused for multiple analysis:

- Automatic and manual analysis of the data extracted to understand the online presence of citizen science.
- Automatic and manual analysis of the data to understand multiple perspectives of citizen science such as Sustainable development goals, research areas or learning promoted.
- The usage and integration of this data to be integrated in an exploratory tool to understand how it supports teachers inspiration during the design of learning activities.

Data and the software developed from **objective 3** might be reused by scientists or educators.

From the point of view of scientific research, the data will be suitable for use by other research groups working on the topics: citizen science, technology-enhanced learning or educational practice. It will also be useful indirectly for researchers on technical aspects of data mining or data extraction.

Within the CS Track Consortium:

The data sets will be shared within the consortium as the working baseline to produce the scientific publications or derived documentation of the studies produced.

Beyond the Consortium:

The data can be used by independent researchers to better understand the contents and conclusions of the scientific publications, which base their findings on the data. Furthermore, the data collected and results from the analysis will be useful for the materials created for the transfer of knowledge workshops or conferences developed for key stakeholders (such as teachers in relation to the integration of sustainable education).

Additionally, as the purpose of the research is to support teachers' inspiration, data will be the source of stimulus for teachers to get inspiration to design learning activities. By the usage of the exploratory tool, data sharing will be useful for their teaching practice.

4.3 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data.

For all the material published in Zenodo it is necessary a web browser and open office tools. For GitHub access, it is necessary a web browser or an IDE with git configuration and repository cloned.

CS projects data classified dataset and software developed from OBJ1: For accessing to the TIC UPF servers, it is necessary to use a VPN and application programming interfaces (API) offered MongoDB storage systems. Nevertheless, the same data is published in Zenodo without restrictions. For academic collaborators, it was installed in the UPF server the open source tool Metabase (<https://www.metabase.com/>) for accessing the data through a web browser.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: Web browser to access to the exploratory tool, Open office tools and audio/video tools.

4.4 Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

All the documentation is provided within the software in the GitHub and also published in

Zenodo.

4.5 Specify which licences you will apply to the data to allow maximum re-use.

Software developed from OBJ1: is published in Github without reuse or access restrictions.

Exploratory tool for OBJ3: The licence that applies to the exploratory tool generated is Creative Commons Attribution - NonCommercial - ShareAlike 4.0 International.

See 4.1 for more information about the data access in Zenodo.

5. Storage and preservation of data

5.1 What criteria will you use to select the data to be preserved in the long term?

The following criteria will be taken into account: The content must be relevant to others, the format must be easy to reuse, the data must be linked to a publication, there must be sufficient time available from the platforms, and there must be sufficient economic resources available.

All the datasets provided by collaborators for OBJ2: data won't be published due to ethical restrictions.

5.2 How long will you keep the data?

Zenodo reported that the retention period is the Lifetime of the Zenodo account, or until the material published will be deleted. Not prior to 20 years.

CS projects data classified dataset from OBJ1: Data storage in the database in the UPF services will be deleted after 3 years. The data storage in CS Track Google Drive will be deleted after 5 years. The data storage in the database in the UPF services will be deleted when the account will be deleted.

All the datasets created by teachers and TEL experts for OBJ3: Hostinger host services offer a year payment plan. Nevertheless, the last version of the software developed will be updated to the GitHub.

5.3 In which repository will you store your data?

Zenodo and GitHub.

References

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